

Design and Performance of Wireless Cooperative Relaying Yearly Report 2011/2012

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Design and Performance of Wireless Cooperative Relaying

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Abstract

This yearly report corresponds to the activities performed in the year 2011/2012. It presents the goals established towards the thesis preparation and the expected outcomes. In July 2009, I presented a proposal for a PhD thesis titled “Design and Performance of Cooperative Relaying”, aiming to investigate: a cooperative 802.11 medium access control protocol able to exploit the knowledge about multi-hop transmission opportunities to augment the throughput and reliability of single antenna wireless systems. This report relates to the thesis work being developed as part of the MAP-Tele doctoral programme. The activities here reported and the work achieved relate to the period between July 2011 and June 2012, corresponding to the third year of the thesis development.

1. Introduction

Next generation wireless networks are expected to provide services that need high performances as well as bandwidth efficiency. This means that as the number of wireless terminals increases, higher system capacity is needed to provide the required data rate levels. However, although wireless networks provide easy connectivity and fast deployment, they still present low performance levels. The major limitation of wireless networks comes from the shared medium, limited-resources devices, and unstable wireless channels. Channel conditions in wireless networks are subjected to fading variations, including interference that can affect both throughput and reliability.

The application of cooperative communications ranges from ad-hoc self organizing networks to vehicular networks, sensor networks and dynamic spectrum management. Technological challenges increase when nodes have intermittent access to a network infrastructure, which can happen in the presence of low data rate stations and in mobile scenarios. In the former case, network performance may decrease since low-data rate devices may grab the radio spectrum for long periods of time. In such situation high-data rate devices may act as relays, helping low-data rate devices to release the spectrum earlier, contributing to increase the overall system performance.

In the case of mobile scenarios, two examples can be provided to show the benefits of applying cooperative communications: vehicular networks and pedestrian networks. In the former example, cars may often leave the range of an Access Point (AP) without terminating their communication sessions. With cooperative communications, cars can relay data to the AP via another car, minimizing packet losses [1] and increasing coverage. In the case of pedestrian mobile networks, mobile devices may perform ping-pong movements at the edge of an AP with high probability, where devices will spend too much time performing handovers between neighbor APs, leading to performance degradation. To avoid such situation, another device can act as relay allowing the moving node to stay always associated to the same AP, avoiding handovers. These examples show the advantages of deploying cooperative communications to improve the utilization of wireless spectrum while providing higher network performance.

Although previous work proves the potential of cooperative diversity in wireless communications, it does only define access methods that would support cooperation on the physical layer. For this propose, the Medium Access Control (MAC) scheme of 802.11 networks must be changed to support a sender-relay-receiver communication model. With such multi-user diversity, instead of sending packets directly to the destination at low transmission rates, senders can transmits at a high rate to a relay, or set of relays, which then forward packets to the destination. Such cooperative relaying MAC schemes can mitigate negative effects of low-data rate devices and multi-path fading, providing better throughput, more reliable communication, as well as improve energy expenses, capacity and outage. However, such benefits are limited since the MAC scheme does not exploit

wireless diversity: the receiver only gets the packet transmitted by the relay, ignoring the packet sent by the source. To overcome this limitation, a solution passes by modify the MAC layer to support cooperation diversity at physical layer. Independently of being used in combination with cooperative diversity schemes, the performance of cooperative relaying strongly depends upon the efficiency of the process used to select one or more relays. This thesis aims to contribute to the investigation of cooperative 802.11 MAC able to exploit the knowledge about multi-hop transmission opportunities in order to augment the throughput and reliability of single antenna wireless systems, while increasing the energy efficiency and range of the overall network.

The remaining of the report is organized as: In Section 2, I describe the scientific contributions. Section 3 details the achievement against the proposed work plan. In section 4 deviation from work plan and updates are described. Section 5 shows comparison between the proposed success indicators and current achievements.

2. Scientific Contributions

After analyzing the problem domain, I have proposed a Cooperative Relaying framework called RelaySpot aiming to provide a solution for the open issues identified in thesis the proposal. A detailed explanation of the proposed RelaySpot framework, was presented in the ACCESS 2011 paper [2].

The proposed framework is called RelaySpot since it does not rely on additional control messages as in the case of prior art [3][4][5] but aims to combine Opportunistic Relay Selection performed by the potential relays, with Relay Scheduling by the destination and Cooperative Relay Switching between the self-elected relays aiming to avoid the deterioration of selected relays. When there is need of cooperation, the RelaySpot framework aims to allow self-elected relays to avoid high interference and to guarantee high data rates to the destination. This framework also allows the use of multiple relays, which is beneficial in cases when one relay fails to forward the frame, increasing delivery probability while preventing waste of network resources. Another functionality of RelaySpot is cooperation between relays, which aims to ensure a high probability of selecting the best set of nodes, as well as to estimate how long a node should be kept in the group of selected relays. In what concerns the relay selection, our metric is not based on CSI as is the case of prior art; we select a relay based on interference, i.e., node degree as well as mobility and history of previous successful transmission to destination. We measure the node degree in connection to load (i.e. active node degree). Thus our aim is to select a relay which guarantees minimum additional resource blockages. In fact, the performance of cooperative relaying in realistic scenarios may be very different from interference-free scenarios that have been the focus of most of the existing proposals so far. Some prior art [5] considers the interference in relay selection, constituting our benchmark to test the relay selection mechanism. The basic building blocks of proposed framework are described in the following subsections.

2.1. Opportunistic Relay Selection

The relay selection process only takes into account nodes that are able to successfully decode packets sent by a source. This ensures that potential relays are closely bounded with the source, with which they have good channel conditions. The qualification of a node as a relay depends upon local information related to node degree, load, mobility and history of transmissions to the specified destination, and not to CSI. Node degree, estimated by overhearing the shared wireless medium, gives an indication about the probability of having successful relay transmissions: having information about the number of neighbors allows the minimization of the collision risk as well as blockage of resources. However, it is possible that nodes with low degree are overloaded due to local processing demands, leading to delay, this is the reason we have considered load (i.e. direct and indirect interference and processing delay).

The goal is to select as relay a node that has low interference factor, which means few neighbors (ensuring low blockage probability), short transmissions and few direct transmissions (ensuring low delays). With the proposed scheme, potential relays opportunistically configure their contention window based on an analysis of direct and indirect interference.

2.2. Relay Scheduling

The opportunistic relay selection mechanism may lead to the qualification of more than one relay, each one with different values of the selection factor, depending on current conditions. Selected relays will forward data towards the destination based on a cooperative relay scheduling mechanism.

Relay scheduling at destination allows self-elected relays to avoid high interference and to guarantee high data rates to a destination while preventing waste of network resources: the contention window plays an important role in scheduling relay opportunities.

Based on the quality of the packets received from all self-elected relays, the destination estimates which of the involved relays are more suitable to help in further transmissions (to get multiple copies the receiver only processes received packets after a predefined time window). The destination sends ACK to source including ID of suitable relay within ACK frame: ACK message with relay identification means that the selected relay will continue sending the following packets. By overhearing the ACK, potential relays that have failed to be selected can compute the Cooperation Factor (CF) of the selected relay and compare with its own CF. This motivates relay switching which is explained in next section.

2.3. Cooperative Relay Switching

As we select relays opportunistically, there is the possibility that a best relay may not be able to compute a small contention window, losing the opportunity to relay the frame. In order to overcome this situation, RelaySpot includes a relay switching operation.

All potential relays are able to compute their own CF (Cooperation Factor), as well as the CF of the currently selected relay. The former is possible by overhear the ongoing RTS/CTS, which are used to compute the cooperation factor from the signal quality. The latter can be computed based on the selected relay's source-relay and relay-destination data rate, that any other relays can collect by overhearing data frames and ACK frames.

If a potential relay is not selected in the cooperative relay scheduling procedure, it compares its cooperation factor with the selected relay's cooperation factor. If its cooperation factor is better, which means that it can provide better gain, it sends a "Data Frame for Relay Switching" to the destination informing about its own cooperation factor. This way the previously selected relay can be switched to the newly selected relay, since by overhearing the frame sent by the new relay, the source will send the next data frame towards that relay.

Relay switching is very suitable for dynamic scenarios where a previously selected relay may not be efficient at some stage, due to mobility, fading, obstacles etc. Hence, unlike other prior-art, relay switching can overcome such variations in network conditions.

3. Proposed Achievements and Current Results

The work developed in this PhD comprises different activities. This section presents these activities, stating whether they have been already concluded, are currently ongoing, or still to be done. Additionally, it provides the expected outcomes and proposed target publications along with current achievements.

- Activity 1: **Related Work Analysis** (July 2009 until September 2009)
 - Expected achievements: Analysis of prior-art in cooperative wireless relaying, including their advantages and limitations in the context of the proposed scenarios and against the defined problem statement.
 - Expected outcome: 1 Technical report and 1 internal presentation.
 - Status: Complete.
 - Achievements:
 - * Analysis of the main families of relay selection approaches
 - * Analysis of the key factors that impact efficiency.
 - Outcomes: 1 poster [6]; 1 Position paper [7]; 1 internal presentation [8].
- Activity 2: **Brainstorming** (September 2009 until December 2009)
 - Expected achievements: Expected to delve into potential enhancements of prior-art and/or into new paradigms, concepts and algorithms. The set of results of this phase will be validated based on analytical tools (e.g. Matlab, simulators) whenever necessary.
 - Expected outcomes: 1 Technical report on novel approaches; 1 workshop publication.
 - Status: Complete
 - Achievements:
 - * Proposed a taxonomy for relay selection approaches.
 - * Analysis of relay selection matrices.
 - Outcomes: 1 workshop publication [9] ;
- Activity 3: **Specification/Validation** (January 2010 until September 2011)
 - Expected achievements: Specification and evaluation of all identified potential solutions, including an objective comparison of the performance of the different design options against related prior-art.
 - Expected outcome until September 2010: 1 Technical report on novel solutions (validation based on simulations); 1 poster publication; 2 conference publications.
 - Expected outcome until September 2011: 1 Technical report on novel solutions (validation based on simulations); 2 conference publications; 1 journal publication.
 - Status: Ongoing.
 - Achievements:

- * Definition of RelaySpot framework:
 - Solution for Opportunistic Relay Selection.
 - Solution for Cooperative Scheduling.
 - Solution for Relay Switching in mobile network.
- * Implementation of Opportunistic Relay Selection and Relay Scheduling in OMNET++ 4.1, MiXim framework.
- Outcomes until June 2011: 1 international conference publication [2]; 1 internal presentation [10]; 1 Poster presentation [11].
- Outcomes until June 2012: 1 international journal publication [12]; 2 international conference publication [13] [14]; 1 internal presentation [15]; 1 oral presentation [16], 1 technical report [17].

The next section presents the deviations from the original proposed work plan and updates.

4. Deviations and Work plan Updates

As the work evolved, some updates needed to be done in the work plan. Thus in this section I present the deviations from the original work plan as well as the updates to keep the work on the right track.

4.1. Deviations

- In what concerns the timeline the initial proposed plan was to complete *Activity 3* until the end of September, 2011. However, I spent more time on simulator (analyzing different frameworks for implementation such as INET and MiXim) and internal outcomes (i.e. preparation of IPR, oral presentations, FCT exploratory project submissions etc), therefore I propose to complete the Activity 3 by end of year 2012.
- In what concerns the presentation of technical reports, I will still present two reports: a first report will include the introduction to cooperative communication, related work analysis and research directions; second technical report will be related to relay simulation and implementations using OMNET++. I plan to finish these two reports until December 2012.
- In what concerns conference publications, from the four conference publications expected in activity 3, I accomplish two conference plus one workshop publication. The missing publication will be submitted until end of September 2012.

4.2. Work plan Updates

The main focus of the thesis is as proposed. However, I planned to investigate Chain Relaying, but instead of implementing Chain Relaying, I decided to work more deeply on the other two functional blocks of RelaySpot: Opportunistic Relay Selection and Cooperative Relay Scheduling. As the work progressed, I came up with the a new component of RelaySpot (relay switching). Therefore, instead of publishing one missing conference publication, I aim to submit two publications plus a survey paper: this survey paper is justified since I already have materiel and analysis to deepen the work done in WiMOB'10 [9]. This publication will be incorporated in first technical report.

- Publications: (until December 2012)
 - 1 Conference paper about Cooperative Relay Scheduling (to be submitted in September 2012, the expected venues can be IEEE WCNC 2013, IEEE ICC 2013, ACM SAC 2013, etc).
 - 1 extra conference paper about RelaySpot Network Capacity studies (to be submitted around December 2012 the expected venues can be IEEE WoWMoM 2013, IFIP Networking 2013, ACM MobiHoc 2013, etc).

- 1 extra Survey paper “Survey and Analysis of Cooperative MAC Protocols” (to be submitted to IEEE Surveys and Tutorials).

5. Scientific Milestones

This section provides a comparison between the proposed success indicators and current achievements so far as well as work under review and to be submitted.

Table 1: Success indicators, proposed targets, and achievements so far.

	Technical Reports	Workshop Publications	Conference Publications	Journal Publication
Proposed Targets	3	1	4	1
Achievements				
2010		WiMOB'10		
2011			ACCESS'11	
2011			CoNEXT'11	
2012	Technical Report1		NTMS'12	IJANS'12
	Technical Report2		4th Paper (Relay Scheduling)	
	Technical Report3		*Paper (Network Capacity)	
			*Survey Paper	

Published:

To be submitted:

Additional paper:

Next section presents the extra achievements throughout the research work.

6. Extra Achievements

- Talk at 5th MAP-Tele workshop, about progress of my work [16].
- Contribution to the first ULOOP white paper about Cooperative Networking [18].
- Contribution to ULOOP paper about resource management [19].
- Submission of FCT exploratory project proposal [20].
- Presentation at ULOOP 3rd plenary meeting about RelaySpot in Resource Management [21].
- Presentation at ULOOP 2nd plenary meeting about Few-hop sharing in Resource Management [22].
- TPC member of ICWMC 2012.
- Submission of “Design and Performance of Wireless Cooperative relaying, progress report MAP-Tele 2010/2011” [23].
- Poster at the 4th, MAP-Tele Workshop, about the progress of my work [11].
- Technical report entitled “UPNs: User-provided Networks, Technical Report: Living-examples, challenges, advantages” [24].
- IAN meeting presentation on the “Redefining CoopMAC” [10].
- Submission of “Design and Performance of Wireless Cooperative relaying, progress report MAP-Tele 2009/2010” [25].
- Submission of FCT yearly reports for year 2011 [26] and for year 2010 [27].
- Presentation of Position paper at IAN Workshop[7].
- IAN meeting presentation on the “Partner’s Selection Schemes” [8].
- Presentation of Poster at the 1st, MAP-Tele Workshop[6].
- Submission of PhD Pre Thesis Proposal [28].
- Submission of FCT BD proposal [29].

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